

STONING SPORTS IN THE MILITARY TRAINING SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article presents a methodology for training military personnel using kettlebell sport. The principles of sports training, which have specific patterns for physical exercise sessions, are described. This article presents a methodology for training military personnel using kettlebell sport. The principles of sports training, which have specific patterns for physical exercise sessions, are described.

Keywords: military personnel, period, load, intensity, weight, jerk, push.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada harbiy xizmatchilarni girya sporti vositalari yordamida tayyorlash uslubi taqdim etilgan. Jismoniy mashg'ulotlarning o'ziga xos qonuniyatlariga ega bo'lgan sport mashg'ulotlari tamoyillari yoritilgan. Maqolada harbiy xizmatchilarni girya sporti vositalari bilan tayyorlash metodikasi batafsil bayon qilingan. Shuningdek, jismoniy mashqlar bilan shug'ullanishning maxsus qonuniyatlariga asoslangan sport mashg'ulotlari tamoyillari atroflicha tavsiflangan.

Tayanch iboralar: harbiy xizmatchilar, davr, yuklama, shiddat, og'irlik, siltab ko'tarish, itarish.

Relevance. The scientific and methodological literature contains a limited number of publications that reveal the features of training methodology for military personnel using kettlebell sport.

Objective of the research: to increase the effectiveness of physical training for military personnel through kettlebell sport.

Task: to identify the features of physical training for military personnel using kettlebell sport during the winter training period.

The physical training of military personnel in the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation is aimed at developing physical qualities and forming military-applied motor skills of service members, taking into account their military-professional activities, gender, and age. [3, p. 3].

As is known, in the theory and methodology of sports training, there are three periods: preparatory, competitive, and transitional. In turn, the preparatory and competitive periods consist of training stages [1, p. 130, 2, p. 58]. The period of preparation and training for military personnel is divided into summer and winter.

Achieving high results in kettlebell sport, as in many other sports, is only possible with good general physical and special training. In this regard, it is of great importance to use certain principles of sports training that have specific patterns for physical exercise sessions, which primarily include such principles as:

- principle of continuity;
- principle of progressive impact;
- principle of cyclicity;
- principle of undulating and variable dynamics of training loads;
- unity of in-depth specialization and orientation of the training process towards high achievements;
- principle of age-appropriate pedagogical influence.

It should be noted that a rational increase in training loads can lead to high sports and technical results. It's important to keep in mind that starting with lighter weights in kettlebell sport allows you to pay more attention to the technical training of military personnel. In other words, this approach employs the "conjugated training method."

When using maximum training loads, not only special physical fitness but also the volitional qualities of military personnel are effectively developed [4, p. 223].

The main objectives of the winter preparation period are:

1. Development of physical qualities: general - GPT (general physical training) and special - SPT (special physical training).
2. Development of mental and moral-volitional qualities.
3. Preparation for passing control standards.
4. Body recovery.
5. Acquisition of knowledge on hygiene, nutrition, self-monitoring, etc.

The winter preparation period of the preparatory training stage is presented, consisting of three phases, illustrating the dynamics of intensity and volume of physical training load, which includes breathing exercises, breathing through additional dead space, breathing with resistance, and voluntary hyperventilation.

Characteristics of the winter preparation period of the preparatory training stage

The general preparatory phase primarily focuses on creating and developing the prerequisites for acquiring peak physical condition, developing the basic motor skills necessary for military personnel to perform training and combat tasks.

In the special preparatory phase, the training process continues to develop motor skills and improve overall physical fitness.

The main training methods at these stages are primarily special preparatory exercises [5, p. 348].

The volume and intensity of training loads increase gradually, with the volume of training loads increasing at a faster rate.

At the end of the second stage of the preparatory period, competitive exercises are used to a greater extent.

Among mesocycles, the following are recommended: introductory, basic, recovery, and recovery-maintenance.

In matters of technical mastery during the preparatory period, the focus is on establishing basic technical training, followed by stages of in-depth technical improvement and achieving high sports and technical mastery.

In psychological training, it is necessary to adhere to the principle that it is important to develop in military personnel a psychological readiness for performing special tasks.

Conclusion. Kettlebell sport in the military training system is a fundamental means of developing professionally important qualities. There is a positive transfer of kettlebell sport training sessions to the combat training activities of military personnel.

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